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Without cytomegalovirus infection, no brain infarction

Short communication

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The evidence published is increasing that infectious agents play an important role in stroke development. Especially human cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection has been repeatedly related to atherosclerosis, hypertension and even stroke. In this study, the relationship between CMV infection and stroke is re-investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

Without cytomegalovirus infection, no brain infarction (BI).

CONCLUSION:

CMV and BI are potentially causally related.

Keywords:

Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

In unfortunate and unfavourable conditions, a blood vessel in the brain leaks or bursts and a hemorrhagic stroke occurs or manifests itself. In contrast to a hemorrhagic stroke, the blood circulation in the brain might suddenly be disrupted by various factors. A blood clot might block or narrow the arteries which are supplying blood and oxygen to the brain. Under these conditions, the brain will get too little or no oxygen and can be permanently damaged (ischaemic stroke). Can infectious agents¹ contribute anything to blood clotting? Nonetheless, discussing a possible relationship between infection and stroke is not really something entirely new. Galen himself (second century A.D.) described apoplexy, which is the Greek term for stroke, as determined by “some inflammatory disease that exists in the head”² perhaps the first reference to stroke as a consequence of infection. Several European neurologists noted in the late 1800s a link between acute infections and stroke, even in children.³ Meanwhile, a multitude of infections is discussed to directly cause stroke, including bacterial (syphilis, tuberculosis), fungal (cryptococcus, aspergillus, mucormycosis), parasitic and cytomegalovirus too. Human cytomegalovirus (CMV) is globally widespread. During the first year of life, CMV seroprevalence is about 40%.⁴ CMV seropositive rate is 66.7% in the USA⁵; while 90.1% in Hans and 95.4% in Kazakhs in Xinjiang Province, China⁶ In point of fact, a primary CMV infection is usually asymptomatic while CMV itself persists throughout life in a number of tissues and leads to the development of a lifelong carrier status with periodic (subclinical) reactivation.⁷

¹Zhen J, Zeng M, Zheng X, Qiu H, Cheung BMY, Xu A, Wu J, Li C. Human cytomegalovirus infection is associated with stroke in women: the US National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 1999-2004. *Postgrad Med J*. 2022 Mar;98(1157):172-176. doi: 10.1136/postgradmedj-2020-139201. Epub 2021 Feb 4. PMID: 33541928.

²Karenberg A, Hort I. Medieval descriptions and doctrines of stroke: preliminary analysis of select sources. Part I: The struggle for terms and theories - late antiquity and early Middle Ages. *J Hist Neurosci*. 1998 Dec;7(113 Pt 2):162-73. doi: 10.1076/jhin.7.3.162.1849. PMID: 11623840.

³Marie P Hémiplégie cérébrale infantile et maladies infectieuses. *Prog Med*. Paris; 1885;13:167-9.

⁴Dolan A, Cunningham C, Hector RD, Hassan-Walker AF, Lee L, Addison C, Dargan DJ, McGeoch DJ, Gatherer D, Emery VC, Griffiths PD, Sinzger C, McSharry BP, Wilkinson GWG, Davison AJ. Genetic content of wild-type human cytomegalovirus. *J Gen Virol*. 2004 May;85(Pt 5):1301-1312. doi: 10.1099/vir.0.79888-0. PMID: 15105547.

⁵Simanek AM, Dowd JB, Pawelec G, Melzer D, Dutta A, Aiello AE. Seropositivity to cytomegalovirus, inflammation, all-cause and cardiovascular disease-related mortality in the United States. *PLoS One*. 2011 Feb 17;6(2):e16103. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0016103. PMID: 21379581; PMCID: PMC3040745.

⁶Tang N, Li JW, Liu YM, Zhong H, Wang LM, Deng FM, Qu YY, Hui J, Cheng J, Tang B, Huang G, Guo SX, Li XZ, Wei LL, He F. Human cytomegalovirus infection is associated with essential hypertension in Kazakh and Han Chinese populations. *Med Sci Monit*. 2014 Dec 2;20:2508-19. doi: 10.12659/MSM.892861. PMID: 25448630; PMCID: PMC4262054.

⁷Britt W. Manifestations of human cytomegalovirus infection: proposed mechanisms of acute and chronic disease. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol*. 2008;325:417-70. doi: 10.1007/978-3-540-77349-8_23. PMID: 18637519.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Li et al.

The Chinese group around Li et al. ⁸ provided data on the relationship between cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection and brain infarction (BI) which are publicly available. Li et al. at the Medical College of Shihezi University, Shihezi, China used among other enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) et cetera to detect CMV infection. Elevated levels of CMV-IgG, CMV-IgM, C-reactive protein (CRP), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), and interleukin-6 (IL-6) are discussed to be related ⁹, ¹⁰, ¹¹, ¹² with cytomegalovirus determined diseases. Data on cardiovascular risk factors, such as smoking status, drinking status et cetera were obtained. All subjects were examined using computed tomography (CT) (GT 1700V, GE Healthcare, USA). A part of the data of Li et al. were re-analysed (see table 1).

⁸Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. *PLoS One*. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

⁹Roberts ET, Haan MN, Dowd JB, Aiello AE. Cytomegalovirus antibody levels, inflammation, and mortality among elderly Latinos over 9 years of follow-up. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2010 Aug 15;172(4):363-71. doi: 10.1093/aje/kwq177. Epub 2010 Jul 21. PMID: 20660122; PMCID: PMC2950794.

¹⁰Simanek AM, Dowd JB, Pawelec G, Melzer D, Dutta A, Aiello AE. Seropositivity to cytomegalovirus, inflammation, all-cause and cardiovascular disease-related mortality in the United States. *PLoS One*. 2011 Feb 17;6(2):e16103. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0016103. PMID: 21379581; PMCID: PMC3040745.

¹¹Mundkur LA, Shivanandan H, Hebbagudi S, Endrsz V, Varma M, Rao V, Gonczol E, Kakkar VV. Human cytomegalovirus neutralising antibodies and increased risk of coronary artery disease in Indian population. *Heart*. 2012 Jul;98(13):982-7. doi: 10.1136/heartjnl-2012-301850. PMID: 22668865.

¹²Cheng J, Ke Q, Jin Z, Wang H, Kocher O, Morgan JP, Zhang J, Crumpacker CS. Cytomegalovirus infection causes an increase of arterial blood pressure. *PLoS Pathog*. 2009 May;5(5):e1000427. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1000427. Epub 2009 May 15. PMID: 19436702; PMCID: PMC2673691.

Table 1. The relationship between CMV IgG and brain infarction (Study of Li et al, 2017).

		Brain infarction		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	193	354	547
	NO	2	14	16
		195	368	563

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,07956651$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,04566002
p (SINE) = 0,99644760
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,98974359
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,87500000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,04566002
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,25
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,02
P Value (SINE) = 0,00354610

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (193 / 547) \times 100 = 35,28 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (354 / 547) \times 100 = 64,72 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (2 / 16) \times 100 = 12,50 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (14 / 16) \times 100 = 87,50 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (193 / 195) \times 100 = 98,97 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (2 / 195) \times 100 = 1,03 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (354 / 368) \times 100 = 96,20 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (14 / 368) \times 100 = 3,80 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (547 / 563) \times 100 = 97,16 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (16 / 563) \times 100 = 2,84 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (195 / 563) \times 100 = 34,64 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (368 / 563) \times 100 = 65,36 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 2,82266910
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,02888599

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 3,81638418
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,01869404

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,31793961
p(IOI) = 0,62522202

The prevalence of CMV of the population studied is about $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (354/368) \times 100 = 96,20\%$. This value is in accordance with the published values of the Chinese ¹³ population. The data of Li et al. are of use.

¹³Tang N, Li JW, Liu YM, Zhong H, Wang LM, Deng FM, Qu YY, Hui J, Cheng J, Tang B, Huang G, Guo SX, Li XZ, Wei LL, He F. Human cytomegalovirus infection is associated with essential hypertension in Kazakh and Han Chinese populations. Med Sci Monit. 2014 Dec 2;20:2508-19. doi: 10.12659/MSM.892861. PMID: 25448630; PMCID: PMC4262054.

2.1.2. Fair study conditions

The study of Li et al. ¹⁴ is very unfair. Under fair study conditions, we should obtain data similar to the following (see table 2). In other words, the data of Li et al. are of some use in this respect.

Table 2. The relationship between CMV IgG and brain infarction (fictive data in blue colour combined with the 2017 Li et al. data).

		Brain infarction		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	193	4880	5073
	NO	2	193	195
		195	5073	5268

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,02778814$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,02155723
 p (SINE) = 0,99962035
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/B)$ > 0,98974359
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/(Not A))$ > 0,98974359

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,02155723
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,02
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,02
 P Value (SINE) = 0,00037958

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (193 / 5073) \times 100 = 3,80 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (4880 / 5073) \times 100 = 96,20 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (2 / 195) \times 100 = 1,03 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (193 / 195) \times 100 = 98,97 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (193 / 195) \times 100 = 98,97 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (2 / 195) \times 100 = 1,03 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (4880 / 5073) \times 100 = 96,20 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (193 / 5073) \times 100 = 3,80 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (5073 / 5268) \times 100 = 96,30 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (195 / 5268) \times 100 = 3,70 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (195 / 5268) \times 100 = 3,70 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (5073 / 5268) \times 100 = 96,30 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 3,70934358
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,02888714

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 3,81649590
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,02778814

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= 0,00000000
 p (IOI)= 0,92596811

¹⁴Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. PLoS One. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*¹⁵ too.

2.2.1. Necessary condition relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a denote the number of observed successes.

Table 3. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	<u>d</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher,

¹⁵Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution¹⁶. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

¹⁶Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

3. Results

3.1. Theorem. Without cytomegalovirus infection, no brain infarction

Theorem 1 (Without CMV infection, no BI).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Without CMV infection, no brain infarction is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

Without CMV infection, no brain infarction is not true.

Proof by the study of Li et al. The data of the study of Li et al. ¹⁷ are statistically analysed (see table 1). The data provided are very unfair ($p(\text{IOU})= 0,31793961$). Nonetheless, the same data are of some use for our purposes. The causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,07956651$; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = $0,04566002$) and does not contradict a necessary condition relationship. The probability ($p(\text{SINE})$) of a necessary condition relationship between CMV and BC is $p(\text{SINE}) = 0,99644760$ and with P Value = $0,00354610$ highly significant. We cannot find any difference between the necessary condition identified within the sample and the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition within the population. The null-hypothesis need to be accepted.

Without CMV infection, no brain infarction (P Value = $0,00354610$).

□

Under conditions of a fair study design (see table 2), the necessary condition relationship between CMV and BI is much stronger ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,99962035$; P Value = $0,00037958$).

¹⁷Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. PLoS One. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

3.2. CMV and treatment

The following proposal of a treatment of a CMV infection should be initiated, supervised and monitored by a medical specialist experienced with the drugs suggested. The scientific justification for the proposed medications can be found somewhere ¹⁸ else.

Table 4. CMV infection: Additional therapy

Data:	Name	First name	Birthday	Place of residence	Phone	E-Mail	Approved by
Drug	Immunoglobulin	Leftunomide	Etoricoxib	Eianercept	Valaciclovir	Atorvastatin	Cimetidin
Dosage	1 g per kg i.v. qd	10 mg qd or 20 mg p.o. qd	30 mg or 90 mg p.o. qd	10 mg or 25 mg or 50 mg s.c.	2 g p. o. qid	80 mg qd	800 mg qd
Month:							
Day:							
1	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
2		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
3	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
4		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
5	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
6		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
7		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
8		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
9		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
10		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
11		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
12		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
13		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
14		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
15		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
16		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
17		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
18		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
19		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
20		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
21		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
22		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
23		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
24		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
25		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
26		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
27		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
28		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
29		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
30		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
31		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0

¹⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer - a causal relationship?. *Causation*, 18(11), 5–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7567432>

4. Discussion

Although at first blush the implications of the sample size when interpreting a study may seem like an overriding concern over other important scientific issues, notably to critical and other reader such concern is utterly justifiable. The issue of the sample size is of paramount importance. A sample size should not be either too big or too small since both have limitations which possess the possibility to compromise the conclusions drawn from such studies. A sample size which is too small may prevent the findings of differences and may tempt us to accept a false premise as true whereas a sample size which is too large may amplify the detection of differences, which are not practically relevant. Bearing these points in mind, there are different methods to calculate an appropriate sample size.¹⁹,²⁰ Nonetheless, even if there is a widespread belief that large samples are more appropriate for research, this is not always true. Very large samples tend to transform something insignificant into something significant. Hence, neither the sample size nor the number of studies considered guarantees logical sound conclusions drawn from studies.

For illustration purposes, let us suppose that a study is investigating the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human being alive. Only three subjects were investigated, the following data were obtained and published.

Table 5. Gaseous oxygen and human being alive

		Human being alive B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen A_t	TRUE	1	1	2
	FALSE	0	1	1
		1	2	3

Under normal circumstances, our confidence into a relationship identified is running high parallel with with an increasing sample size. In contrast to a very large sample size, even a study with a very small sample size ($N = 3$) or even one single study is capable of identifying a fundamental relationship i. e. between gaseous oxygen and human life, it depends as always on the concrete circumstances. Human experience teaches us however that the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life as established before is true even if the sample size of the study presented is extremely small. As is well known, it is rarely possible to study the entire population. Nonetheless, further studies despite of a larger sample size must be able to confirm the relationship established before in principle, independently of potential difficulties. Indeed, establishing scientific evidence is central to any scientific inquiry but not as simple as desired. In general, it is known that data of one single study might be enough to refute a whole theory or a theorem but are very rarely suitable enough to convince the reader

¹⁹Hajian-Tilaki K. Sample size estimation in diagnostic test studies of biomedical informatics. *J Biomed Inform.* 2014 Apr;48:193-204. doi: 10.1016/j.jbi.2014.02.013. Epub 2014 Feb 26. PMID: 24582925.

²⁰Pandis N, Polychronopoulou A, Eliades T. Sample size estimation: an overview with applications to orthodontic clinical trial designs. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2011 Oct;140(4):e141-6. doi: 10.1016/j.ajodo.2011.04.021. PMID: 21967951.

of a discovered everlasting truth. However the truth might be, it is at least somewhat difficult to convince the majority of the scientific community of fundamental evidence found while relying on one single study. Nevertheless, if we consider only the data of one single study at this point, it is only to direct readers attention to a possible interesting relationship, but by no means a proof of a perpetual truth. However, theorems, theories or scientific claims should be testable by observational evidence. In other words, considerable progress is possible and should be made in order to elucidate the relationship between CMV and BI further in more detail.

5. Conclusion

In fact, our degree of confidence by which we are convinced to know the answers to very important questions tend to vary systematically with various factors. In particular, as established by this investigation, it might be appropriate to consider as true the following null hypothesis:

Without cytomegalovirus infection, no brain infarction.

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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